

Joint Power Allocation and Splitting (JoPAS) for SWIPT in Time-Variant Wireless Channels

Dexin Wang*, Xiang Cheng[†] and Liuqing Yang*

*Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO 80523

[†] State Key Laboratory of Advanced Optical Communication Systems and Networks,

School of Electronics Engineering and Computer Sciences, Peking University, Beijing 100871, P. R. China

Emails: dxwang@engr.colostate.edu, xiangcheng@pku.edu.cn, lqyang@engr.colostate.edu

Abstract—In recent years, the capacity and charging speed of batteries have become the bottleneck of mobile communications systems. With the development of wireless power transfer technologies, simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) becomes a possible alternative. Due to the limitations of practical circuit implementation, the energy harvesting circuit cannot directly decode the information carried by the same signal. Hence, the problem of optimal power splitting at the receiver arises in addition to the conventional problem of power allocation in communication systems. In this paper, the joint power allocation and splitting (JoPAS) for SWIPT over a time-variant channel is proposed with the objective of maximizing the achievable data rate with constraints on the delivered power. Simulations show significantly improved performance compared with the existing dynamic power splitting scheme. A suboptimal algorithm, named decoupled power allocation and splitting (DePAS), is also proposed with dramatically reduced computational complexity and simulations demonstrate its near-optimum performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, mobile devices in wireless communication systems are powered by batteries. Unfortunately, however, the development in the portable energy storage industry is stagnant compared with the vibrant wireless communications industry. In addition, the limited capacity of batteries dramatically hinders the application of the rapidly developing wireless communication technologies [1]. On the other hand, for decades, the solutions to prolong the lifetime of battery-powered wireless devices are confined to battery replacement or wired charging, which are inconvenient or sometimes even challenging for mobile devices. Wireless power transfer (WPT) attracts people's attention for its potential to provide a more convenient, safer and more environment friendly alternative [2] and is a promising solution for green communication.

Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) have drawn significant interest in the field of wireless communications, signal processing and networking etc. because of its potential to extend the lifetime of energy constraint systems. With SWIPT, useful information and electric power can be transferred by the same radio-frequency (RF) signals simultaneously. Varshney first proposed to transfer energy and information with the same signal in [3]. Grover et al. studied the inherent and non-trivial rate-energy tradeoff in the power allocation problem in SWIPT for frequency-selective channels [4]. The tradeoff between the optimal allocation for highest

Shannon capacity and for highest efficiency of power transfer is investigated. In this work, it was assumed that there is no loss of power on observing the signal for information decoding (ID). To the best of our knowledge, however, practical circuits for energy harvesting (EH) from radio signals are not yet capable of directly decoding the carried information. As a result, two practical circuit designs, namely time switching (TS) and power splitting (PS), were proposed in [5]. In [6] and [7], the authors extended the work to a dynamic power splitting (DPS) scheme, which dynamically splits the received signal into two streams, for ID and EH respectively, with varying splitting factors over time. The rate-energy tradeoff is investigated by means of the rate-energy (R-E) region in the context of flat-fading time-invariant channel.

Nonetheless, the time-invariant channel assumption may not be valid in many applications. It is well-recognized that channel fading is a major factor that limits the performance of wireless communication systems. Channel estimation works well under slow fading conditions. Under fast fading conditions, however, the channel state information (CSI) estimated by the receiver often becomes obsolete at the time of transmission. For example, in vehicular communications, as the movement speed of the vehicles increases, the channel coherence time decreases [8]. For a vehicle moving at highway speed (75 mph or 120 km/h) with carrier frequency of 5.9 GHz, the 50% channel coherence time is only 0.65 ms. For time-variant channels, the proposition in [6] that static power splitting (SPS) scheme is the optimal DPS scheme no longer holds. On the other hand, the existing schemes could not accommodate the time-variant channel condition with optimal performance. Therefore, studying the optimal power allocation and splitting factor in these scenarios is necessary for the application of SWIPT in more general settings. Channel prediction was brought to attention by [9, 10]. And it has brought significant improvement in the performance of communication systems [11]. Therefore, we propose to utilize the information made available by channel prediction and consider the channel fading over time for SWIPT.

In this paper, we investigate the power allocation at the transmitter and power splitting at the receiver for SWIPT over time-variant channels in a point-to-point system. We first transform the original optimization problem into a convex one. From its dual problem and the KKT conditions, we discovered

some interesting resemblance between the optimal solution for SWIPT and the waterfilling scheme for traditional communication system power allocation. In light of these conclusions, a suboptimal algorithm named decoupled power allocation and splitting (DePAS) is also proposed. In contrast to JoPAS, it first splits the total transmission power in the time window into two parts for ID and EH, respectively. Then the two parts of power are allocated to each time slot separately, with different optimization strategies for ID and EH respectively. Simulations demonstrate that DePAS achieves near-optimum performance with dramatically reduced computational complexity.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The system model and assumptions are introduced in Section II. The JoPAS is proposed and analyzed in Section III. Section IV proposes a low-complexity sub-optimal heuristic algorithm that achieves near-optimal solution. Simulations presented in Section V demonstrate the correctness of our derivation and proofs. Comparisons between the proposed algorithms and the dynamic power splitting (DPS) [6] is also conducted to show the improvement of our proposed algorithms. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the problem of simultaneously power and information transfer over a flat-fading time-variant wireless channel, the channel efficiency at time instance k is defined as $\eta_k = |h_k|^2$, where h_k is the channel response at time slot k . In this paper, we will focus on DPS, as TS is a special case of DPS and achieves a smaller rate-energy tradeoff region [6].

Different from the problem with time-invariant channels, for the time-variant channel η , we model the problem as a joint optimization of power allocation and SWIPT power splitting factor that maximizes the data rate capacity for ID within a window of N time slots. We assume the future channel responses in the window of length N are available via channel prediction. The formulation of the optimization problem is

$$\underset{\mathbf{P}, \boldsymbol{\rho}}{\text{maximize}} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{(1 - \rho_k) \eta_k P_k}{\sigma^2} \right) \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} P_k \leq P_{\text{total}}, \quad (1b)$$

$$\rho_k \in [0, 1], \quad (1c)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \rho_k \eta_k P_k \geq P_{\text{del}}, \quad (1d)$$

$$0 \leq P_k \leq P_{\text{max}}, \quad (1e)$$

$$k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1, \quad (1f)$$

where P_k denotes the transmission power at time slot k and σ^2 is the variance of the additive white Gaussian noise generated by the down conversion circuits at the receiver. The antenna noise is usually much weaker than the down conversion noise. Hence, it is ignored in this work. Without loss of generality, the energy harvest efficiency is assume to be 1 for simplicity of the analysis, since it is just a constant positive scalar that does not affect the structure and properties of the problem.

The constraint (1b) limits the total transmission power during the N -slot time window. ρ_k represents the portion of power split to energy harvesting at the receiver and (1c) ensures its range from 0 to 1. (1d) states that the total delivered power to the receiver must exceed P_{del} . The constraints described by (1e) circumscribe the instantaneous transmission power for each time slot below P_{max} .

III. JOINT POWER ALLOCATION AND SPLITTING

Since the objective function of the maximization problem is non-concave in (1), it is a non-convex optimization problem and, hence, is difficult to solve efficiently. Nonetheless, we can equivalently reformulate (1) into a convex form

$$\underset{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}}{\text{minimize}} \quad - \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \ln(\sigma^2 + \eta_k Q_k) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} P_k \leq P_{\text{total}}, \quad (2b)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \eta_k (P_k - Q_k) \geq P_{\text{del}}, \quad (2c)$$

$$P_k \leq P_{\text{max}}, \quad (2d)$$

$$0 \leq Q_k \leq P_k, \quad (2e)$$

$$k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1, \quad (2f)$$

and ρ_k can then be obtained by $\rho_k = 1 - \frac{Q_k}{P_k}$.

The convex optimization problem in (2) can be solved efficiently by many existing numerical algorithms. In order to develop a deeper understanding of the problem and the tradeoffs in the problem, we derive the dual problem and apply the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions.

To derive an interesting dual problem, we first reformulate (2) once more as

$$\underset{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}}{\text{minimize}} \quad \tilde{R}(\mathbf{Q}) = \begin{cases} -\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \ln(\sigma^2 + \eta_k Q_k), & \mathbf{Q} \geq \mathbf{0}; \\ \infty, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad Q_k - P_k \leq 0, k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1,$$

$$P_k - P_{\text{max}} \leq 0, k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1,$$

$$P_{\text{del}} - \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \eta_k (P_k - Q_k) \leq 0,$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} P_k - P_{\text{total}} \leq 0.$$

By moving the lower bound on \mathbf{Q} to the objective function, fewer dual variables will be introduced and, thus, facilitate our analysis of the problem.

Theorem 1. *The dual problem of (3) is*

$$\underset{\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta}{\text{maximize}} \quad g(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta) \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \alpha + \mu_k - \eta_k \lambda_k - \eta_k \beta = 0, \quad (4b)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda} \geq \mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\mu} \geq \mathbf{0}, \alpha \geq 0, \beta \geq 0. \quad (4c)$$

where

$$g(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \ln(\lambda_k + \beta) - \sigma^2 \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\lambda_k + \beta) - P_{\max} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \mu_k - P_{\text{total}}\alpha + P_{\text{del}}\beta + N \quad (5)$$

Proof. See Appendix A. \square

By applying the KKT conditions to the primal-dual pair and exploiting the zero duality gap, we have

Theorem 2. For any P_k^* strictly less than P_{\max} ,

$$(1 - \rho_k^*)P_k^* = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^*} - \frac{\sigma^2}{\eta_k} \right)^+, \quad (6)$$

where $(\cdot)^+$ denotes $\max(0, \cdot)$ and α^* is the optimizer of the dual problem (4).

Proof. See Appendix B. \square

Note that α^* is a constant with respect to k . The righthand side of (6) is of the same form of the waterfilling scheme, which is proven to be the optimal power allocation scheme for conventional communication systems. Therefore, Theorem 2 tells us that the power allocated for ID follows a pattern similar to the waterfilling scheme over time when the maximum transmission power is not reached. Intuitively, it is desirable for the purpose of EH to allocate all the power to the time slot with largest η_k , referred to as the best time slot. Whereas for the purpose of ID, the optimal power allocation is waterfilling, which favors time slots with larger η_k by allocating more power to them, but also allocates some power to time slots with smaller η_k to exploit the extra transmission time.

Therefore, the optimal power allocation for SWIPT would only use the best time slot for power transfer and allocate the remaining power with the waterfilling scheme, if there were no constraints on maximum instant transmit power (2d). Nonetheless, with the constraints in (2d), the ID and EH will have to compete for the transmission power at time slots with larger η_k when the maximum instant transmit power is reached, meaning $P_k = P_{\max}$.

In such situations, neither the ID nor the EH part can transmit the optimal amount of power. Instead, they will have to compromise to achieve the optimal solution. Part of the power to be transmitted for EH will shift to other time slots with lower η_k . And that for ID will also deviate from the waterfilling solution.

IV. DECOUPLED POWER ALLOCATION AND SPLITTING

Although the JoPAS problem is convex, the complexity to solve it is still $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$. Whereas the complexity of the waterfilling algorithm for traditional power allocation problems is only $\mathcal{O}(N)$. On the other hand, according to Theorem 2, the power allocation for ID follows a pattern similar to waterfilling except at time slots where $P_k = P_{\max}$. In this section, we propose a heuristic low-complexity algorithm,

named decoupled power allocation and splitting (DePAS), to obtain a sub-optimal solution to the problem in (2).

In this algorithm, we first split the total transmission power in the N time slots according to a factor ρ . For the part of power split for ID, waterfilling scheme is adopted to calculate the power for ID at each time slot. For the other part of power, time slots with higher η_k is adopted with priority. If the transmission power at the best time slot reaches P_{\max} , the channel with the next largest η_k is used for the remaining power and so on. Then value of the overall power splitting factor ρ is adjusted until the required power delivery P_{del} is achieved. The detailed algorithm description is presented in Algorithm 1. In Secion V, simulations show that the performance of the DePAS is almost as good as the JoPAS.

Algorithm 1 DePAS

Initialize $\rho \leftarrow \rho_0$;

repeat

Split $(1 - \rho)P_{\text{total}}$ for ID and allocate Q_k by the waterfilling algorithm

for all $Q_k > P_{\max}$ **do**

$Q_k \leftarrow P_{\max}$

end for

Try to transmit the remaining power for EH over the time slots with largest η_k -s as long as the constraints $P_k \leq P_{\max}$ hold.

Compute $\tilde{P}_{\text{del}} \leftarrow \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \eta_k (P_k - Q_k)$.

if $\tilde{P}_{\text{del}} < P_{\text{del}}$ **then**

Increase ρ

else

Decrease ρ

end if

until The delivered power matches P_{del}

Calculate $\rho_k = 1 - \frac{Q_k}{P_k}$.

V. SIMULATIONS

We consider a point-to-point link in vehicular communications, with the vehicle moving at a speed of 120 km/h, which is the typical speed on highways. The carrier frequency is set to 5.9 GHz and the bandwidth is 10 MHz. The time-variant channel is generated according to the Jake's model.

A. JoPAS

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show the optimal transmit power allocation and power splitting factors at the receiver. In the figures, the black bars denotes the ratio $\frac{\sigma^2}{\eta_k}$, which is a visualization of the channel conditions at each time slot. In the meantime, it is the varying term at the righthand side of (6), which can be seen as the ‘‘riverbed’’ of the waterfilling scheme.

From the results, we observe the same phenomenon as described in Theorem 2. The optimal power allocation for information transfer, represented by the blue bars in the figures, always shows similar pattern as the regular waterfilling scheme wherever the maximum transmission power limit is not reached. At the time slots where P_{\max} is reached, on the

Fig. 1: JoPAS solutions at high SNR.

Fig. 2: JoPAS solutions at low SNR.

other hand, the power allocation shows obvious differences from the waterfilling scheme, e.g. the time slot where $k = 4$ in Fig. 1 and the time slots where $k = 3, 4$ in Fig. 2. This simulation verifies the correctness of our derivation and the proof of Theorem 2.

B. Comparisons

To demonstrate the effectiveness of JoPAS and DePAS, we compare them with the DPS scheme [6], which allocates transmission power evenly and optimizes the splitting factor ρ_k at each time slot.

In this comparison, we set the total transmission power $P_{\text{total}} = N$. P_{del} is set to vary from 0 to $0.5P_{\text{total}}$ respectively. The average rates for ID are shown in Fig. 3. From the results, we observe that, compared with DPS, both JoPAS and DePAS improves the capacity for ID while satisfying the same requirement on EH, especially when larger amount of EH is

required. This is because that the DPS only utilize the channel information for power splitting factor optimization and the power allocation is not adapted according to the channel information. Additionally, the achievable rate of DePAS is close to that of JoPAS while dramatically reduces the computational complexity from $\mathcal{O}(N^3)$ to $\mathcal{O}(N)$.

Besides the comparison of the average rate, we take a closer look at the rate-energy tradeoff for a given channel. For an instance of the time-variant channel η in $N = 10$ time slots, the achievable R-E regions at high SNR and low SNR are presented in Fig. 4. At the high-rate end of the curves in Fig. 4, where $P_{\text{del}} = 0$, the difference between JoPAS and DPS in achievable rate decreases as SNR increases. This is reasonable since the optimal power allocation in JoPAS, the waterfilling scheme, is close to uniform allocation as σ^2/η_k is almost zero across all k -s, and the DPS just allocates P_{total}/N to each time slot.

Fig. 4 shows that both DePAS and JoPAS achieves much larger R-E region than DPS. For this given channel η , the R-E region difference between DePAS and JoPAS is negligible.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed to jointly optimize the power allocation and splitting factor for simultaneous information and power transfer over time-variant channels. By reformulation, the problem is transformed into a convex optimization problem. We then derived the dual problem and proved that the power allocated for ID follows the waterfilling scheme at time slots when the maximum instant transmission power constraint is not active. Simulations verified our analyses and demonstrated that JoPAS achieves much larger R-E region than DPS over time-variant channels and, hence, provides improved flexibility and more efficient usage of the channel, especially at low SNR. In addition, we proposed algorithm DePAS that achieves almost the same R-E region with much lower computational complexity compared with JoPAS.

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APPENDIX A PROOF OF THEOREM 1

The Lagrangian is presented in (7). Let

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial Q_k} = -\frac{\eta_k}{\sigma^2 + \eta_k Q_k} + \lambda_k + \beta \eta_k = 0, \quad (8)$$

we have

$$Q_k^* = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_k + \beta \eta_k} - \frac{\sigma^2}{\eta_k} \right)^+, \quad (9)$$

where Q_k^* is the optimum Q_k that minimizes the Lagrangian (7) and $(\cdot)^+$ denotes the function $\max(0, \cdot)$. Therefore, we have

$$\tilde{g}(\lambda, \mu, \alpha, \beta) = \inf_{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}} L(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}, \lambda, \mu, \alpha, \beta) \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta) &= \tilde{R}(\mathbf{Q}) + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \lambda_k (Q_k - P_k) + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \mu_k (P_k - P_{\max}) + \alpha (\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} P_k - P_{\text{total}}) + \beta (P_{\text{del}} - \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \eta_k P_k + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \eta_k Q_k) \\
&= \tilde{R}(\mathbf{Q}) + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\lambda_k + \eta_k \beta) Q_k + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} (\alpha + \mu_k - \lambda_k - \eta_k \beta) P_k - P_{\max} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \mu_k - P_{\text{total}} \alpha + P_{\text{del}} \beta
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Fig. 3: Average rate (Mbps) achieved by JoPAS and DePAS in comparison with DPS

Fig. 4: Achievable Rate-Energy regions of DPS, JoPAS, and DePAS

Substituting (9) into (7) yields

$$\tilde{g}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta) = \begin{cases} g(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta), & \alpha + \mu_k - \lambda_k - \eta_k \beta = 0, \forall k; \\ -\infty, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Therefore, the dual problem

$$\text{maximize } \tilde{g}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \alpha, \beta)$$

is equivalent to (4).

APPENDIX B PROOF OF THEOREM 2

Obviously, Slater's condition holds as there exist a strictly feasible point for the primal problem. Let $(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \alpha^*, \beta^*)$ represents the optimizer of the dual problem (4). Therefore, the optimizer for the primal problem is

$$(\mathbf{P}^*, \mathbf{Q}^*) = \arg \inf_{\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}} L(\mathbf{P}, \mathbf{Q}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \alpha^*, \beta^*). \tag{11}$$

Given the Q_k^* in (9) and substitute λ_k according to the constraints in (4b), we have

$$Q_k^* = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_k^* + \alpha^*} - \frac{\sigma^2}{\eta_k} \right)^+. \tag{12}$$

On the other hand, by applying the KKT condition on the primal dual pair (3) and (4), we have complementary slackness [12].

$$\mu_k^* (P_k^* - P_{\max}) = 0. \tag{13}$$

Therefore, for any P_k^* strictly less than P_{\max} , $\mu_k = 0$ and, hence, $Q_k^* = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^*} - \frac{\sigma^2}{\eta_k} \right)^+$, which exactly is the form of waterfilling solutions.

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